

Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints (modern)

By Kevin Pepper, Blinn College

Entry tags: Religious Group, (The) Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, Christian Traditions, Latter Day Saints (Mormons)

Latter-day Saints, more commonly known as "Mormons", are a sect of Christianity whose spiritual beliefs include an open scriptural canon, modern-day revelation, additional scripture, temple worship, divine priesthood authority, and a church structure that is a restoration of the Primitive Church of Jesus Christ.

Date Range: 1951 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Global

Region tags: Global

Region spanning the globe.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Book of Mormon
- Source 2: The Doctrine and Covenants
- Source 3: The Pearl of Great Price

Notes: While Latter-day Saints also use the King James Version of the Bible as an authoritative/canonical text, the preceding texts form the scriptural canon that is unique to Mormonism.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.lds.org/?lang=eng>
- Source 1 Description: Official website for The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.mormon.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Website that explores basic beliefs, doctrines, and principles of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The canonical texts of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the King James version of the Bible, The Book of Mormon, The Doctrine and Covenants, and The Pearl of Great Price; they are also referred to as the Standard Works because they comprise the Christian standard of behavior for Latter-day Saints.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: The canonical texts of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the King James version of the Bible, The Book of Mormon, The Doctrine and Covenants, and The Pearl of Great Price; they are also referred to as the Standard Works because they comprise the Christian standard of behavior for Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly

Father.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

— Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. Latter-day Saint theology includes an open, continuous canon that is based on revelation from God to His Prophet.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

— Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

— Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

— Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

— No

Notes: There is no professional theological/seminary in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

— Yes

Notes: The canonical texts of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the King James version of the Bible, The Book of Mormon, The Doctrine and Covenants, and The Pearl of Great Price; they are also referred to as the Standard Works because they comprise the Christian standard of behavior for Latter-day Saints.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

— Yes

Notes: Sites connected with the Restoration—the time from the life of Joseph Smith to when the Latter-day Saints left Nauvoo, Illinois (approximately early to mid-19th century)—are preserved as sacred sites by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. They are non-religious, historical structures that are open to the public. Sites also important to The Church in countries aside from the United States are also preserved. Temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are also sacred sites; however, they function solely as religious structures and are not open to the public after they are dedicated.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Latter-day Saints exist all across the globe and are not congregated, as in the early days of the Church, in a single area; therefore, this percentage would vary greatly depending on the location of the various congregations around the world.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

— Square meters: 253015

Notes: These dimensions are for the Salt Lake City Temple; this temple is the most well-recognized Latter-day Saint structure to non-adherents.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

— Height, meters: 68

Notes: These dimensions are for the Salt Lake City Temple; this temple is the most well-recognized Latter-day Saint structure to non-adherents.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 38182

Notes: Latter-day Saint temples vary greatly in size. Of all the temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints currently in operation, the average size of temple would be roughly 38,182.81 square feet.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 22

Notes: Latter-day Saint temples vary greatly in size. Of all the temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints currently in operation, the average size of temple would be roughly 22.33 square feet.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Latter-day Saints exist all across the globe and are not congregated, as in the early days of the Church, in a single area; therefore, this percentage would vary greatly depending on the location of the various congregations around the world.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are taught to be respectful of cultural difference, yet, at the same time, to eliminate individual cultural practices that are not in harmony with the Gospel of Jesus Christ as taught in their scriptural canon and by the General Authorities of the Church.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are taught to be respectful of cultural difference, yet, at the same time, to eliminate individual cultural practices that are not in harmony with the Gospel of Jesus Christ as taught in their scriptural canon and by the General Authorities of the Church.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are taught to be respectful of cultural difference, yet, at the same time, to eliminate individual cultural practices that are not in harmony with the Gospel of Jesus Christ as taught in their scriptural canon and by the General Authorities of the Church.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints, as a whole, are non-violent religious group who strive to solve conflict peacefully and in harmony with the teachings of Jesus Christ; however, that does not preclude them from participating in warfare or other armed conflicts if needed for the defense of their own lives, their families, or their country.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: While individual members may act violently in their own communities, the Church, as a whole, does not engage in conflict--violent or otherwise--with any cultural, political, social, or economic groups.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Altars:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The Conference Center, along with Temple Square, in Salt Lake City are the largest mass gathering points for members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Areas, and structures, important to early Church history are preserved by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16118169

Notes: The total Church membership in 1951 was 1,147,157; in the last available statistical report, from May 2018, total Church membership was 16,118,169.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: While a person might be "born in the covenant"--which means that their parents are both Latter-day Saints and that they were married in a LDS temple--children are not considered members until they are baptized at the age of 8. The choice to be baptized is left solely to the child after they have been taught about the covenants, responsibilities, and promises extended to those who are member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Like many other Christian religions, Latter-day Saints invite everyone to participate in the Gospel of Jesus Christ; each person has to choose for themselves whether to accept the Gospel--and make the covenants associated with that choice--or to reject it. Latter-day Saints do not violate any individual's choices on membership in the Church.

↳ Assigned by class:

— No

Notes: Any individual who wants to make covenants with God--regardless of any social position, label, or standing--is welcome to join the Church.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

— Yes

Notes: While a person might be "born in the covenant"--which means that their parents are both Latter-day Saints and that they were married in a LDS temple--children are not considered members until they are baptized at the age of 8. The choice to be baptized is left solely to the child after they have been taught about the covenants, responsibilities, and promises extended to those who are member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Assigned by gender:

— No

Notes: While there are individual organizations within the Church for men and women, any individual who wants to make covenants with God--regardless of any social position, label, or standing--is welcome to join the Church.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

— Yes

Notes: Individuals who want to join the Church are admitted through baptism--a rite performed by a male who holds the Priesthood authority to act in the name of God--which represents the death, burial, and Resurrection of Jesus Christ. There is no alternative way to become a member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

— No

Notes: Individuals who want to join the Church are admitted through baptism--a rite performed by a male who holds the Priesthood authority to act in the name of God--which represents the death, burial, and Resurrection of Jesus Christ. There is no alternative way to become a member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— Yes

Notes: Church membership is reported annually and includes adult members, children of record (children who are born to Latter-day Saints parents but have not been baptized), and converts (individuals above the age of 9 who have been baptized).

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

— No

Notes: There are no religious professionals--in the sense that the Church is run by a lay ministry

and that a seminary/theological degree is not required to administer the Church in any ecclesiastical position--within The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

— No

Notes: While proselytizing is a part of an individual member's official missionary service--which is, generally, from ages 18-25 for single males, from age 19 for single females, and/or after a married couple has no children remaining in their home for which they are primarily responsible--individual members are not required to proselyte regardless of ecclesiastical position.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

— No

Notes: There are no religious professionals--in the sense that the Church is run by a lay ministry and that a seminary/theological degree is not required to administer the Church in any ecclesiastical position--within The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. There are, however, General Authorities who are primarily responsible for missionary work around the globe and who no longer participate in their previous professions; their full-time, daily responsibilities are to be witnesses--which is what missionary work is in a general sense--for the Gospel of Jesus Christ around the globe.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

— Yes

Notes: Members are encouraged to complete a full-time mission as either young adults or senior couples. Members are also taught to share the Gospel often, and sincerely, with individuals wherever/whenever they can.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

— No

Notes: Latter-day Saints respect the personal choices of other individuals and never coerce individuals to become members of the Church.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

— Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.002

Notes: There are 7.6 billion people in the world currently; as of May 2018, Latter-day Saints account for 16,118,169 of the world population.

Does the religion have official political support

— No

Notes: The Church does not support, and is not endorsed by, any specific political party, platform, or position.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

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↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian groups, Latter-day Saints have apostates. Apostates are individuals who have denied teachings, practices, or membership in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. Prolonged, belligerent, or repeated apostasy is subject to discipline in from the Church and, at it's most extreme form, leads to excommunication.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian groups, Latter-day Saints have apostates. Apostates are individuals who have denied teachings, practices, or membership in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. Prolonged, belligerent, or repeated apostasy is subject to discipline in from the Church and, at it's most extreme form, leads to excommunication.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– No

Notes: While individual members might shun or vilify apostates, the Church does not shun or vilify apostates publicly or privately.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

Notes: If membership in the Church is considered a form of social capital--in the sense that it allows you access to resources of a particular social group--then, in a general sense, the Church could be seen as "revoking" social capital through excommunication; however, it is doubtful if the individuals members themselves would agree with the previous interpretation/assertion.

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

Notes: Revocation of membership--with the associated covenants, blessings, and responsibilities--is the only punishment apostates receive.

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Religious apostasy, by definition, would incur some sort of divine displeasure and that, in itself, could be seen as a punishment.

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: A renunciation of faith in Jesus Christ, and/or a failure to strive to live the Gospel He taught, will not allow an individual to return to live with Heavenly Father again. In Latter-day Saint theology being eternally separated from God, through a lack of faith, personal choices, or a combination of the two, could be seen as a form of "punishment"; as in most Christian religions, failure to return to live with God could be categorized as a "punishment".

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, while Heavenly Father does/can curse individuals or groups, the circumstances of mankind are dictated by their individual moral/immoral choices. Just as individuals are blessed for their righteousness, they can also be cursed for their wickedness.

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

Notes: While there are other supernatural beings inside Latter-day Saint theology, curses would be pronounced by Heavenly Father whether those curses are extended by human servants or other divine messengers.

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Removal of membership in the Church and revocation of priesthood, and temple, blessings during an individual's mortal life which would, in turn, lead to real consequences in the Kingdom of God after death.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: All temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are dedicated structures that are for sacred religious purposes exclusively and are closed to the general public; meetinghouses are also dedicated for worship purposes only and are open to the general public.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to ecological features:

– No

Notes: In most of the temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, the orientation is not by ecological feature but by direction. Most of the temples are oriented to face the east due to the doctrine that the Second Coming of Christ will begin starting in the east.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: While Latter-day Saints may visit sacred sites as individuals, families, or groups, the concept of pilgrimages doesn't exist in the doctrine of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are taught to be respectful of cultural difference, yet, at the same time, to eliminate individual cultural practices that are not in harmony with the Gospel of Jesus Christ as taught in their scriptural canon and by the General Authorities of the Church.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are taught to be respectful of cultural difference, yet, at the same time, to eliminate individual cultural practices that are not in harmony with the Gospel of Jesus Christ as taught in their scriptural canon and by the General Authorities of the Church.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are taught to be respectful of cultural difference, yet, at the same time, to eliminate individual cultural practices that are not in harmony with the Gospel of Jesus Christ as taught in their scriptural canon and by the General Authorities of the Church.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints, as a whole, are non-violent religious group who strive to solve conflict peacefully and in harmony with the teachings of Jesus Christ; however, that does not preclude them from participating in warfare or other armed conflicts if needed for the defense of their own lives, their families, or their country.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: While individual members may act violently in their own communities, the Church, as a

while, does not engage in conflict--violent or otherwise--with any cultural, political, social, or economic groups.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: While a person might be "born in the covenant"--which means that their parents are both Latter-day Saints and that they were married in a LDS temple--children are not considered members until they are baptized at the age of 8. The choice to be baptized is left solely to the child after they have been taught about the covenants, responsibilities, and promises extended to those who are member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Like many other Christian religions, Latter-day Saints invite everyone to participate in the Gospel of Jesus Christ; each person has to choose for themselves whether to accept the Gospel--and make the covenants associated with that choice--or to reject it. Latter-day Saints do not violate any individual's choices on membership in the Church.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Any individual who wants to make covenants with God--regardless of any social position, label, or standing--is welcome to join the Church.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: While a person might be "born in the covenant"--which means that their parents are both Latter-day Saints and that they were married in a LDS temple--children are not considered members until they are baptized at the age of 8. The choice to be baptized is left solely to the child after they have been taught about the covenants, responsibilities, and promises extended to those who are member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: While there are individual organizations within the Church for men and women, any individual who wants to make covenants with God--regardless of any social position, label, or standing--is welcome to join the Church.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals who want to join the Church are admitted through baptism--a rite performed by a male who holds the Priesthood authority to act in the name of God--which represents the death, burial, and Resurrection of Jesus Christ. There is no alternative way to become a member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

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Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Church membership is reported annually and includes adult members, children of record (children who are born to Latter-day Saints parents but have not been baptized), and converts (individuals above the age of 9 who have been baptized).

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There are no religious professionals--in the sense that the Church is run by a lay ministry and that a seminary/theological degree is not required to administer the Church in any ecclesiastical position--within The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: While proselyting is a part of an individual member's official missionary service--which is, generally, from ages 18-25 for single males, from age 19 for single females, and/or after a married couple has no children remaining in their home for which they are primarily responsible--individual members are not required to proselyte regardless of ecclesiastical position.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There are no religious professionals--in the sense that the Church is run by a lay ministry and that a seminary/theological degree is not required to administer the Church in any ecclesiastical position--within The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. There are, however, General Authorities who are primarily responsible for missionary work around the globe and who no longer participate in their previous professions; their full-time, daily responsibilities are to be witnesses--which is what missionary work is in a general sense--for the Gospel of Jesus Christ around the globe.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Members are encouraged to complete a full-time mission as either young adults or senior couples. Members are also taught to share the Gospel often, and sincerely, with individuals wherever/whenever they can.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints respect the personal choices of other individuals and never coerce individuals to become members of the Church.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Church does not support, and is not endorsed by, any specific political party, platform, or position.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian groups, Latter-day Saints have apostates. Apostates are individuals who have denied teachings, practices, or membership in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. Prolonged, belligerent, or repeated apostasy is subject to discipline in from the Church and, at it's most extreme form, leads to excommunication.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

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↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– No

Notes: While individual members might shun or vilify apostates, the Church does not shun or vilify apostates publicly or privately.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

Notes: If membership in the Church is considered a form of social capital--in the sense that it allows you access to resources of a particular social group--then, in a general sense, the Church could be seen as "revoking" social capital through excommunication; however, it is doubtful if the individuals members themselves would agree with the previous interpretation/assertion.

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

Notes: Revocation of membership--with the associated covenants, blessings, and responsibilities--is the only punishment apostates receive.

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Religious apostasy, by definition, would incur some sort of divine displeasure and that, in itself, could be seen as a punishment.

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: A renunciation of faith in Jesus Christ, and/or a failure to strive to live the Gospel He taught, will not allow an individual to return to live with Heavenly Father again. In Latter-day Saint theology being eternally separated from God, through a lack of faith, personal choices, or a combination of the two, could be seen as a form of "punishment"; as in most Christian religions, failure to return to live with God could be categorized as a "punishment".

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, while Heavenly Father does/can curse individuals or groups, the circumstances of mankind are dictated by their individual moral/immoral choices. Just as individuals are blessed for their righteousness, they can also be cursed for their wickedness.

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

Notes: While there are other supernatural beings inside Latter-day Saint theology, curses would be pronounced by Heavenly Father whether those curses are extended by human servants or other divine messengers.

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Removal of membership in the Church and revocation of priesthood, and temple, blessings during an individual's mortal life which would, in turn, lead to real consequences in the Kingdom of God after death.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16118169

Notes: The total Church membership in 1951 was 1,147,157; in the last available statistical report, from May 2018, total Church membership was 16,118,169.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.002

Notes: There are 7.6 billion people in the world currently; as of May 2018, Latter-day Saints account for 16,118,169 of the world population.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The canonical texts of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the King James version of the Bible, The Book of Mormon, The Doctrine and Covenants, and The Pearl of Great Price; they are also referred to as the Standard Works because they comprise the Christian standard of behavior for Latter-day Saints.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: The canonical texts of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the King James version of the Bible, The Book of Mormon, The Doctrine and Covenants, and The Pearl of Great Price; they are also referred to as the Standard Works because they comprise the Christian standard of behavior for Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly

Father.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, all scripture that is canonical comes through direct communication from God to His prophets, both ancient and modern. These revelations may also be transmitted to prophets by angels under the express direction of Heavenly Father.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. Latter-day Saint

theology includes an open, continuous canon that is based on revelation from God to His Prophet.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: While any member may apply scriptural teachings to their own individual circumstances, binding interpretation of scripture for the entire Church can only be issued from the current Prophet of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: There is no professional theological/seminary in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The canonical texts of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the King James version of the Bible, The Book of Mormon, The Doctrine and Covenants, and The Pearl of Great Price; they are also referred to as the Standard Works because they comprise the Christian standard of behavior for Latter-day Saints.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Sites connected with the Restoration—the time from the life of Joseph Smith to when the Latter-day Saints left Nauvoo, Illinois (approximately early to mid-19th century)—are preserved as sacred sites by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints. They are non-religious, historical structures that are open to the public. Sites also important to The Church in countries aside from the United States are

also preserved. Temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are also sacred sites; however, they function solely as religious structures and are not open to the public after they are dedicated.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Latter-day Saints exist all across the globe and are not congregated, as in the early days of the Church, in a single area; therefore, this percentage would vary greatly depending on the location of the various congregations around the world.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 253015

Notes: These dimensions are for the Salt Lake City Temple; this temple is the most well-recognized Latter-day Saint structure to non-adherents.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 68

Notes: These dimensions are for the Salt Lake City Temple; this temple is the most well-recognized Latter-day Saint structure to non-adherents.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 38182

Notes: Latter-day Saint temples vary greatly in size. Of all the temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints currently in operation, the average size of temple would be roughly 38,182.81 square feet.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 22

Notes: Latter-day Saint temples vary greatly in size. Of all the temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints currently in operation, the average size of temple would be roughly 22.33 square feet.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Latter-day Saints exist all across the globe and are not congregated, as in the early days of the Church, in a single area; therefore, this percentage would vary greatly depending on the location of the various congregations around the world.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Altars:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Notes: The temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are the primary religious monuments in Latter-day Saint theology.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The Conference Center, along with Temple Square, in Salt Lake City are the largest mass gathering points for members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Areas, and structures, important to early Church history are preserved by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Notes: Iconography in The Church of Jesus Christ would generally include representations of any of the stories, settings, or people in the Standard Works (comprised of the Bible, Book of Mormon, Doctrine and Covenants, and Pearl of Great Price), historical events of significance to the Church, representations of doctrine or commandments, and limited representation of Deity outside of the context of the Standard Works.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: All temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are dedicated structures that are for sacred religious purposes exclusively and are closed to the general public; meetinghouses are also dedicated for worship purposes only and are open to the general public.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to ecological features:

– No

Notes: In most of the temples of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, the orientation is not by ecological feature but by direction. Most of the temples are oriented to face the east due to the doctrine that the Second Coming of Christ will begin starting in the east.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: While Latter-day Saints may visit sacred sites as individuals, families, or groups, the concept of pilgrimages doesn't exist in the doctrine of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saint theology believes in the biblical prophecy of the Second Coming of Jesus Christ.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The specific time, date, and place of the return of Jesus Christ are unknown; however, Latter-day Saints believe that the return of Jesus Christ will happen in "the latter-days" and is imminent.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Jesus Christ will reign over the Earth as the geopolitical leader of the entire globe.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Jesus Christ will be the spiritual leader of the entire globe.

↳ Other purpose:

–Yes [specify]: To usher in the end of the world by destroying the wicked

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is omniscient and is concerned with the moment-to-moment behaviors of the human family.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: The Word of Wisdom requires abstinence from alcohol, coffee, tea, tobacco, and harmful drugs; it also encourages a balanced diet and moderation in consumption of other foods.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, sacred structures called "temples" are holy places that only members who are in good standing, and who are in possession of a temple recommend, may enter; they are considered physical tabernacles where God may dwell on Earth and are called "The House of the Lord".

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Objects, like the temple clothing and garments, are considered sacred in Latter-day Saint theology and are protected by covenants made with God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His

children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden.

↳ Other sexual practices:

–Yes [specify]: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is

vitaly concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitaly concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitaly concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitaly concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitaly concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitaly concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, supernatural beings would include demons, Lucifer/Satan, angels, The Holy Ghost, Jesus Christ, and Heavenly Father.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: Although Heavenly Father lives in Heaven, which is above the Earth, He is not associated with any particular connection to any natural phenomenon.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Heavenly Father is not associated with any particular connection to any natural phenomenon or physical location.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is not fused, physically, with any individual.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is not fused, physically, with any individual.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is not fused, physically, with any individual or family; no family grouping can claim direct physical descent from Him.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is only loyal to individuals who make, and honor, sacred covenants with Him.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

— Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and

omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father actively shapes the events of humankind and is profoundly concerned with the daily lives, and difficulties, of each of His children. He actively intervenes in the affairs of humans either directly, through His messengers, or by inspiring humans to take action.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father can bless the righteous and curse the wicked.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father can bless the righteous and curse the wicked.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father actively shapes the events of

humankind and is profoundly concerned with the daily lives, and difficulties, of each of His children. He actively intervenes in the affairs of humans either directly, through His messengers, or by inspiring humans to take action.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father can, and does, get angry with the wickedness of His children. However, anger isn't seen as a negative emotion in and of itself; how anger is expressed can be negative, though. Likewise, Heavenly Father is saddened by the way humans treat each other; sadness also isn't a negative emotion; expressions of sadness might have negative impacts, though. So, Heavenly Father possesses negative emotions but does not engage in negative expressions of emotion.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father, while He has a glorified, perfected physical body, does not need to eat.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the purpose of life is to prepare to return to live with Heavenly Father again after death. He is the one, and only, true God. Therefore, worshiping another deity would be counter-productive to the eternal salvation and exaltation of humankind.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, or though the study of the scriptures.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal. In the most general sense, prayer is a form of divination because it is seeking to know, and understand, the Will of God.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, do not have clearly delineated powers; however, they are either past, or future, inhabitants of this world and

have, at least, that knowledge of this world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: While Satan and his demonic horde of fallen spirits are real and exist in Latter-day Saint theology, they were also created in the image of Heavenly Father. Therefore, while not human in the same sense as the mortals who inhabit this planet, they do look like humans (two arms, two legs, etc.).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Jesus Christ is the only individual who would qualify for this designation; He is the literal offspring of Heavenly Father--a divine Being--and Mary--a mortal being.

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the doctrine of the Godhead is present. The Godhead is composed of three distinct Beings: Heavenly Father, Jesus Christ, and the Holy Ghost. Heavenly Father and Jesus Christ have physical, perfected, immortal bodies and can only occupy one place at any given time or space; the Holy Ghost has a body of spirit and can exist everywhere simultaneously.

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The general social norms of Latter-day Saints would be found in the Gospel of Jesus Christ as contained in their scriptural canon and as interpreted by the Prophet.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ is taught both weekly in formal church meetings and in the home. The Gospel of Jesus Christ is also absorbed daily through striving to live in harmony with its principles and precepts, through daily study of the scriptures, and through prayer.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of

Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

—All individuals (any time period)

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the doctrine is that all individuals in the human family will be judged according the Gospel of Jesus Christ regardless of the time in which they lived; in connection to that idea, each individual will receive an opportunity to completely understand the Gospel, accept or reject it, and to be fairly judged based on their actions and intentions. Therefore, moral norms, which are set by Heavenly Father, are unchangeable but applied correctly to all members of the human family through divine knowledge, justice, mercy, and compassion.

Belief in afterlife:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the afterlife exists in two general stages. Before the Second Coming of Jesus Christ, human spirits are separated into two areas: spirit prison and spirit paradise. Spirit prison is a holding existence for human spirits who either did not hear the Gospel in their mortal lives or who did not accept it while in their mortal lives. They are taught the Gospel of Jesus Christ and are given the opportunity to accept or reject the Gospel. Spirit prison is not "Hell" nor is it a place of suffering. Spirit paradise is a place of rest for those who were faithful to the Gospel of Jesus Christ during their mortal lives. The spirits in spirit paradise travel to spirit prison where they instruct the human spirits there in the Gospel of Jesus Christ. After the Second Coming of Jesus Christ, and the Final Judgment of humanity, the souls of the human family are assigned to three distinct kingdoms of glory. The Celestial Kingdom is the highest kingdom of glory; it is where Heavenly Father dwells and is reserved for those who accepted the Gospel of Jesus Christ and remained faithful throughout their mortal lives. The Terrestrial Kingdom is the middle kingdom of glory; it is reserved for those who accepted the Gospel of Jesus Christ but who were not faithful throughout their mortal lives. The Telestial Kingdom is the lowest degree of glory; it is reserved for those who rejected the Gospel of Jesus Christ. Outer Darkness is not a kingdom of glory; it is reserved for Satan, his demons, and those who rejected Jesus Christ and the Gospel of Jesus Christ.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

— No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

— No

Notes: Curses, in a general sense, could be seen as "punishments"; but, those curses flow from only one supernatural being: Heavenly Father.

Reincarnation in this world:

— No

Notes: Latter-day Saint theology does not believe in reincarnation or in the transmigration of the soul. When humans die, their spirit and body separate; when they are resurrected, their spirits and bodies reunite and become inseparable. The complete soul is comprised of the physical mortal body and the spiritual immortal body.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

— No

Notes: Blessings, in a general sense, could be seen as "rewards"; but, those blessings flow from only one supernatural being: Heavenly Father.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Interment:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

–Yes [specify]: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, no additional sacrifices of goods or individuals, is necessary upon the death, and burial, of another faithful member.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: While faithful Latter-Day Saints are buried in ceremonial clothing connected with covenants made with God, grave goods would be based on individual cultural practices and are not standardized in the Church.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ As cenotaphs:

— No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ In cemetery:

— Yes

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

— No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

— No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Other formal burial type:

— No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; therefore, any righteous human characteristic that would fit within the scope of the Gospel of Jesus Christ, which He revealed through His Son, is espoused by Latter-day Saints.

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: Only in relation to how it might serve others or further the Kingdom of God.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Only in relation to how it might serve others or further the Kingdom of God.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Only in relation to how it might serve others or further the Kingdom of God.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than

other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the body and the spirit are two inseparably connected entities. The spirit is eternal, intangible, is made of matter that is too fine for human perception, is a direct offspring of Heavenly Father, and inhabits the physical bodies of all mortals. The body is mortal, tangible, is made of matter of matter that is perceptible to humans, is a direct offspring of human parents, and dies when the spirit inhabiting it leaves. The spirit and the body are identical in appearance to each other. The soul is comprised of the body and spirit together.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the afterlife exists in two general stages. Before the Second Coming of Jesus Christ, human spirits are separated into two areas: spirit prison and spirit paradise. Spirit prison is a holding existence for human spirits who either did not hear the Gospel in their mortal lives or who did not accept it while in their mortal lives. They are taught the Gospel of Jesus Christ and are given the opportunity to accept or reject the Gospel. Spirit prison is not “Hell” nor is it a place of suffering. Spirit paradise is a place of rest for those who were faithful to the Gospel of Jesus Christ during their mortal lives. The spirits in spirit paradise travel to spirit prison where they instruct the human spirits there in the Gospel of Jesus Christ. After the Second Coming of Jesus Christ, and the Final Judgment of humanity, the souls of the human family are assigned to three distinct kingdoms of glory. The Celestial Kingdom is the highest kingdom of glory; it is where Heavenly Father dwells and is reserved for those who accepted the Gospel of Jesus Christ and remained faithful throughout their mortal lives. The Terrestrial Kingdom is the middle kingdom of glory; it is reserved for those who accepted the Gospel of Jesus Christ but who were not faithful throughout their mortal lives. The Telestial Kingdom is the lowest degree of glory; it is reserved for those who rejected the Gospel of Jesus Christ. Outer Darkness is

not a kingdom of glory; it is reserved for Satan, his demons, and those who rejected Jesus Christ and the Gospel of Jesus Christ.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the planet Earth will be glorified after the Second Coming of Jesus Christ; it will become the Celestial Kingdom and individuals who lived worthy of a celestial glory will inherit it.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saint theology does not believe in reincarnation or in the transmigration of the soul. When humans die, their spirit and body separate; when they are resurrected, their spirits and bodies reunite and become inseparable. The complete soul is comprised of the physical mortal body and the spiritual immortal body.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Interment:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-

day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, no additional sacrifices of goods or individuals, is necessary upon the death, and burial, of another faithful member.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: While faithful Latter-Day Saints are buried in ceremonial clothing connected with covenants made with God, grave goods would be based on individual cultural practices and are not standardized in the Church.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: Burial practices vary culturally among Latter-day Saints across the globe. Faithful Latter-day Saints may be buried anywhere; however, they are dressed, and buried, in ceremonial clothing after death. The ceremonial clothing is sacred and connected to covenants made with God in LDS temples.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, supernatural beings would include demons, Lucifer/Satan, angels, The Holy Ghost, Jesus Christ, and Heavenly Father.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: Although Heavenly Father lives in Heaven, which is above the Earth, He is not associated with any particular connection to any natural phenomenon.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Heavenly Father is not associated with any particular connection to any natural phenomenon or physical location.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is not fused, physically, with any individual.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is not fused, physically, with any individual.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is not fused, physically, with any individual or family; no family grouping can claim direct physical descent from Him.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is only loyal to individuals who make, and honor, sacred covenants with Him.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of

human affairs:

– No

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Heavenly Father is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He comprehends completely the scientific and spiritual aspects of all reality.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father actively shapes the events of humankind and is profoundly concerned with the daily lives, and difficulties, of each of His children. He actively intervenes in the affairs of humans either directly, through His messengers, or by inspiring humans to take action.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father can bless the righteous and curse the wicked.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father can bless the righteous and curse the wicked.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father actively shapes the events of humankind and is profoundly concerned with the daily lives, and difficulties, of each of His children. He actively intervenes in the affairs of humans either directly, through His messengers, or by inspiring humans to take action.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father can, and does, get angry with the wickedness of His children. However, anger isn't seen as a negative emotion in and of itself; how anger is expressed can be negative, though. Likewise, Heavenly Father is saddened by the way humans treat each other; sadness also isn't a negative emotion; expressions of sadness might have negative impacts, though. So, Heavenly Father possesses negative emotions but does not engage in negative expressions of emotion.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father, while He has a glorified, perfected physical body, does not need to eat.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the purpose of life is to prepare to return to live with Heavenly Father again after death. He is the one, and only, true God. Therefore, worshiping another deity would be counter-productive to the eternal salvation and exaltation of humankind.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the theocratic ruler of the entire universe and all reality. He is also called God, God the Father, or The Father. He possesses every good human characteristic in complete perfection; additionally, He is omniscient, omnipresent (through His Spirit), and omnipotent. He is a glorified Being with a tangible, physical body that is immortal and incorruptible. He is also the spiritual Father of all humankind who are His children; Jesus Christ is both a spiritual, and

physical, offspring of Him. Mortals were created in His express image.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, or though the study of the scriptures.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal. In the most general sense, prayer is a form of divination because it is seeking to know, and understand, the Will of God.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His

children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father communicates with His children through His Spirit. This communication can be in the form of dreams, visions, revelations, priesthood blessings, prayer, though the study of the scriptures, or through his appointed servants both mortal and immortal.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, do not have clearly delineated powers; however, they are either past, or future, inhabitants of this world and have, at least, that knowledge of this world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Notes: Angels, which are present in Latter-day Saint theology, include messengers sent from Heavenly Father who inhabited this world in the past, who have yet to inhabit this world, or those who have inhabited this world and have died. Their purpose is to relay divine messages or perform specific actions for/to mankind under the sole direction of Heavenly Father. Any interaction that they have with mankind, either physical or spiritual, would be with express permission of Heavenly Father.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: While Satan and his demonic horde of fallen spirits are real and exist in Latter-day Saint theology, they were also created in the image of Heavenly Father. Therefore, while not human in the same sense as the mortals who inhabit this planet, they do look like humans (two arms, two legs, etc.).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Jesus Christ is the only individual who would qualify for this designation; He is the literal offspring of Heavenly Father--a divine Being--and Mary--a mortal being.

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the doctrine of the Godhead is present. The Godhead is composed of three distinct Beings: Heavenly Father, Jesus Christ, and the Holy Ghost. Heavenly Father and Jesus Christ have physical, perfected, immortal bodies and can only occupy one place at any given time or space; the Holy Ghost has a body of spirit and can exist everywhere simultaneously.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is omniscient and is concerned with the moment-to-moment behaviors of the human family.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: The Word of Wisdom requires abstinence from alcohol, coffee, tea, tobacco, and harmful drugs; it also encourages a balanced diet and moderation in consumption of other foods.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, sacred structures called "temples" are holy places that only members who are in good standing, and who are in possession of a temple recommend, may enter; they are considered physical tabernacles where God may dwell on Earth and are called "The House of the Lord".

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Objects, like the temple clothing and garments, are considered sacred in Latter-day Saint theology and are protected by covenants made with God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His

paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned

with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; He is vitally concerned with the salvation and exaltation of the entire human family who are His children. Therefore, He encourages the development of righteous behaviors and is concerned with eliminating wickedness among His children; the eternal well-being of His children is His paramount purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Curses, in a general sense, could be seen as "punishments"; but, those curses flow from only one supernatural being: Heavenly Father.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Blessings, in a general sense, could be seen as "rewards"; but, those blessings flow from only one supernatural being: Heavenly Father.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saint theology believes in the biblical prophecy of the Second Coming of Jesus Christ.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The specific time, date, and place of the return of Jesus Christ are unknown; however, Latter-day Saints believe that the return of Jesus Christ will happen in "the latter-days" and is imminent.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Jesus Christ will reign over the Earth as the geo-political leader of the entire globe.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Jesus Christ will be the spiritual leader of the entire globe.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: To usher in the end of the world by destroying the wicked

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The general social norms of Latter-day Saints would be found in the Gospel of Jesus Christ as contained in their scriptural canon and as interpreted by the Prophet.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ is taught both weekly in formal church meetings and in the home. The Gospel of Jesus Christ is also absorbed daily through striving to live in harmony with its principles and precepts, through daily study of the scriptures, and through prayer.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: The Gospel of Jesus Christ, in Latter-day Saint theology, was a demonstration of

Heavenly Father's love as embodied, and taught, by His Son, Jesus Christ. The norms associated with the Gospel, therefore, originate with Heavenly Father and are vehicles to allow all of the human family to become like Him and return to live with Him again.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, the doctrine is that all individuals in the human family will be judged according the Gospel of Jesus Christ regardless of the time in which they lived; in connection to that idea, each individual will receive an opportunity to completely understand the Gospel, accept or reject it, and to be fairly judged based on their actions and intentions. Therefore, moral norms, which are set by Heavenly Father, are unchangeable but applied correctly to all members of the human family through divine knowledge, justice, mercy, and compassion.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Latter-day Saint theology, Heavenly Father is the source of all good in the universe; therefore, any righteous human characteristic that would fit within the scope of the Gospel of Jesus Christ, which He revealed through His Son, is espoused by Latter-day Saints.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: Only in relation to how it might serve others or further the Kingdom of God.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Only in relation to how it might serve others or further the Kingdom of God.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Only in relation to how it might serve others or further the Kingdom of God.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are to remain celibate before marriage and to have sexual relations with only their legal husband or wife after marriage.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are to remain celibate before marriage and to have sexual relations with only their legal husband or wife after marriage.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Males and females are required to remain monogamous after marriage; committing adultery is grounds for excommunication for any member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Males and females are required to remain monogamous after marriage; committing adultery is grounds for excommunication for any member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden and constitutes possible grounds for excommunication for any member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Any other sexual relationship--outside of the legal marriage between one man and one woman--is forbidden and constitutes possible grounds for excommunication for any member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saint males, while they may be circumcised based on individual preference or cultural norms, are never castrated to become full members of the Church.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are asked to fast once a month, on the first Sunday of the month, to help relieve the suffering of the poor, needy, and afflicted. Latter-day Saints can also fast whenever they feel the desire for increased divine insight, to develop spiritual strength, or for help in overcoming significant problems in their lives or the lives of others.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: The Word of Wisdom requires abstinence from alcohol, coffee, tea, tobacco, and harmful drugs; it also encourages a balanced diet and moderation in consumption of other foods.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Those who wish to become members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints do not have to be harmed, in any way, to become a fully-fellowshipped member.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: There is no form of painful ritual required to become a member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is present, or proper, in the theology of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is present, or proper, in the theology of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Membership in The Church of Jesus Christ requires making covenants with God and then keeping those covenants for the rest of an individual's mortal life.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: The law of tithing and the law of the fast are two commandments that deal with the sacrifice of economic means to further the work of God.

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: The law of tithing--which asks a member to donate 10% of their increase to the Church to further the work of God--funds buildings, church materials, congregation budgets, and other costs necessary to administering the Church.

To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: The law of the fast--which asks a member to abstain from food and drink for two meals and then donate the cost of those meals to the Church--is designated for relief of the poor and needy. That relief is distributed to members of the Church as well as non-members.

Destroyed:

– No

Notes: Monetary donations, whether tithes or fast offerings, are considered as sacred and are only used for approved purposes; they are, in no way, destroyed.

Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints are asked to serve in specific responsibilities in their respective congregations--called "callings"--that are unpaid volunteer ministries within specific organizations. Members are also expected to attend their weekly meetings and engage in daily devotion as well (prayer, scripture reading, etc.).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: While Latter-day Saints might be victims of violence for their beliefs, membership in the Church does not require physical danger.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Ethical precepts, in Latter-day Saint theology, would be the commandments of the Gospel of Jesus Christ as contained in the scriptural canon and as interpreted by the Prophet.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: While Latter-day Saints might be marginalized for their beliefs, it is not a requirement for membership or fellowship.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: There are no small-scale rituals that would be performed privately by members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: While not all rituals are public--those performed in a Latter-day Saint temple, for instance, are largely private/small--most rituals include more than just the individual and often others who are significant/close to that person.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ritual size is dependent on lots of variables: location, relationships, public/private nature of the ritual, purpose, and time.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ritual frequency is dependent on lots of variables: location, relationships, public/private nature of the ritual, purpose, and time. Some rituals, for instance the Sacrament, are performed weekly and as a congregation; others, like baptism, are performed once and with family and friends of the individual member.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The priesthood-holder who is responsible for orthodoxy is designated by the presiding authority (or may be the presiding authority himself) and would be responsible for making sure the ordinance/rite is performed using the proper language, with the proper priesthood authority, and with the proper movement/signs.

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↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Without further examples of what synchronic practices might be, this question is unanswerable.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: The Word of Wisdom, a basic commandment of the Church, prohibits the use of an intoxicants for personal or religious reasons.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: While there are no special changes to physical appearance in association with membership in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, members who have been endowed in a LDS temple wear sacred garments under their regular clothing. The garments represent holy covenants made between the individual member and God.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

|

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

— Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints refer to other members of the Church as "brother" or "sister" followed by their last name; for example, "Brother Pepper" or "Sister Johnson". In the early days of the Church, members referred to each other by the same moniker "brother/sister" and instead used the first name of the individual; for example, "Brother Joseph" or "Sister Emma".

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

— Yes

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↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

— No

Notes: The standard way to address members of the Church is "brother" or "sister" followed by their last name. This way of referencing other members is culturally common in the Church and acceptable worldwide.

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

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↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

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Notes: Ritual size is dependent on lots of variables: location, relationships, public/private nature of the ritual, purpose, and time.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

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Notes: Ritual frequency is dependent on lots of variables: location, relationships, public/private nature of the ritual, purpose, and time. Some rituals, for instance the Sacrament, are performed weekly and as a congregation; others, like baptism, are performed once and with family and friends of the individual member.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The priesthood-holder who is responsible for orthodoxy is designated by the presiding authority (or may be the presiding authority himself) and would be responsible for making sure the ordinance/rite is performed using the proper language, with the proper priesthood authority, and with the proper movement/signs.

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↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

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E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

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Notes: While there are no special changes to physical appearance in association with membership in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, members who have been endowed in a LDS temple wear sacred garments under their regular clothing. The garments represent holy covenants made between the individual member and God.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints refer to other members of the Church as "brother" or "sister" followed by their last name; for example, "Brother Pepper" or "Sister Johnson". In the early days of the Church, members referred to each other by the same moniker "brother/sister" and instead used the first name of the individual; for example, "Brother Joseph" or "Sister Emma".

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↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: The standard way to address members of the Church is "brother" or "sister" followed by their last name. This way of referencing other members is culturally common in the Church and acceptable worldwide.

Society and Institutions

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithing--giving 10% of an individual's increase to the Church to further the work of God--is a basic tenet of Latter-day Saint theology.

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The Church has no military presence; individual members may be part of their respective nations/states military forces, however.

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same economic processes to secure resources (housing, food, utilities, etc.) as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: While there is distinct vernacular, slang, and religious terminology present--both standardized and region/culture-specific--in the Church, there is no language common to all Latter-day Saints

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints use the calendars of their native cultures; since the Church was founded in the United States, the Church uses the Gregorian Calendar as its official calendar.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a formal religious hierarchy that flows throughout The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints; all positions in that hierarchy are non-elected positions.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same economic processes to secure resources (housing, food, utilities, etc.) as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same economic processes to secure resources (housing, food, utilities, etc.) as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

— Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The Church has no military presence; individual members may be part of their respective nations/states military forces, however.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints use the calendars of their native cultures; since the Church was founded in the United States, the Church uses the Gregorian Calendar as its official calendar.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same military protection, and subjugation, as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The Church runs a large-scale international welfare program that is officially owned/operated by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The Church runs a large-scale international welfare program that is officially owned/operated by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a formal religious hierarchy that flows throughout The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints; all positions in that hierarchy are non-elected positions.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithing--giving 10% of an individual's income to the Church to further the work of God--is a basic tenet of Latter-day Saint theology.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These would be culture, country, legal system or time specific.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, legal, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The Church has no military presence; individual members may be part of their respective nations/states military forces, however.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Church has no military presence; individual members may be part of their respective nations/states military forces, however.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same military protection, and subjugation, as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: While there is distinct vernacular, slang, and religious terminology present--both standardized and region/culture-specific--in the Church, there is no language common to all Latter-day Saints

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints use the calendars of their native cultures; since the Church was founded in the United States, the Church uses the Gregorian Calendar as its official calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints use the calendars of their native cultures; since the Church was founded in the United States, the Church uses the Gregorian Calendar as its official calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same economic processes to secure resources (housing, food, utilities, etc.) as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same economic processes to secure resources (housing, food,

utilities, etc.) as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Latter-day Saints are regular citizens in their respective cities, states, or countries and have interactions with individuals of various cultural, economic, political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational groups daily; they rely on the same economic processes to secure resources (housing, food, utilities, etc.) as non-Latter-day-Saint individuals do.